

A CASE STUDY ON NUTЕК INDIA LIMITED, REGARDING DEEP FALL IN SHARE PRICE

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ABSTRACT

Manipulating the security price is an act of artificially inflating or deflating the price of a security. Generally, manipulation is defined as a series of transactions designed to raise or lower a price of a security or to give the appearance of trading for the purpose of inducing others to buy or sell. In essence, a manipulation is intentional interference with the free forces of supply and demand. In this paper we have tried to study the reasons behind drastic fall in share price of Nutek India Limited.

Keywords: NTIL, Nutek, Price Manipulation, GDR, SEBI.

1. INTRODUCTION:

NTIL is a telecom infrastructure services company providing rollout solutions for both fixed and wireless telecom networks. NTIL provides expertise in turnkey site build, active equipment implementations, operations & maintenance and technical support services. The company’s core expertise lies in the breadth of services it offers in the telecom infrastructure space. It offers services to telecommunication equipment manufacturers, telecom operators as well as third party infrastructure leasing companies in installing and maintaining telecom network equipment & Infrastructure. NTIL is also involved in creation of In-building networks for the Wireless and Data Applications. Its client list constitutes all the prominent players in the telecom industry that includes Third Party Infrastructure Leasing Companies (like Indus Towers, Quippo, WTTIL), Telecom operators (like Airtel, Vodafone, Idia, Reliance Communications, Aircel) and Telecom Equipment Manufacturers (like Ericsson, Nokia Siemens Network, Huawei, ZTE, Motorola)[16].

2. FACTS:

The share was listed at 192 rupees with FV 10 on 27th August 2008. In the mean time, splitted the FV to 5.00 (on 23rd December, 2009). The price of share fallen drastically from IPO listing price, Rs 192 to all time low of Rs 0.65 in BSE[12] and Rs 0.70 in NSE[13] on 25th Nov 2011. The book value of the share is Rs. 32.

TABLE 1: MONTH WISE PRICE VARIATION IN NITL STOCK

Month	Highest Close Price	Month	Highest Close Price	Month	Highest Close Price
August-08	199.3	November-09	96.15	February-11	14.6
September-08	207.6**	December-09	91	March-11	12.69
October-08	80.05	January-10	45.75	April-11	12.72
November-08	61.05	February-10	35.95	May-11	9.23
December-08	55.05	March-10	33.2	June-11	5.98
January-09	49.9	April-10	42.75	July-11	6.32
February-09	41.5	May-10	39.1	August-11	4.31
March-09	33.1	June-10	34.85	September-11	3.14
April-09	47.95	July-10	36.15	October-11	3.28
May-09	57.9	August-10	38.85	November-11	1.35
June-09	59.55	September-10	46.8	December-11	1.48
July-09	63.1	October-10	60.35	January-12	1.49
August-09	63.05	November-10	38.3	February-12	1.12**
September-09	107.1	December-10	23.9		
October-09	103.4	January-11	17.3		

*: Lowest of 43 months

** : Highest of 43 months

Figure 1: Highest closing price of a month

3. FACTORS:

Following are some factors which could be the predictors to detect the factual reason of drastic downfall in the stock price.

(i) Price Manipulation by Operators:

The bulk/block deals data is given below (Table 2) from NSE[13] since beginning of IPO and for the past one year from BSE[12]. Upon carefully analyzing the data, it is evident that following traders/individuals might have deliberately attempted to manipulate the share price while trading.

TABLE 2: BULK/BLOCK DEALS OF IPO THROUGH DIFFERENT INVESTMENT ORGANIZATIONS

S.No.	Name of Trading Entity	Qty of Shares			Average Price (Rs.) of		
		Bought	Sold	Still Holding	Bought	Sold	Still Holding
1	ALFA FISCAL SERVICES PVT LTD (Trading Period-10 th Nov. 2010 to 28 th Oct., 2011). (Trading Avg. Price-Rs. 32.49 to 1.53)	1,24,37,467	1,07,06,269	17,31,200	9.12	9.98	3.79
2	DAVE CHETAN LAXMIKANT (Trading Period- 13 th Oct 2011 to 28 th Oct., 2011).(Trading Avg. Price-Rs. 3.76 to 1.5)	1,09,85,164	92,89,511	16,95,653	2.39	2.2	3.45
3	OVERALL FINANCIAL CONSULTANTS PRIVATE LIMITED (Trading Period-7 th September, 2011 to 26 th Oct., 2011).(Trading Avg. Price-Rs. 3.31 to 1.57)	88,76,105	78,73,939	10,02,166	2.85	2.51	5.56
4	TRANS FINANCIAL RESOURCES LIMITED* (Trading Period-28 th September, 2010 to 16 th March, 2011).(Trading Avg. Price-Rs. 61.75 to 10.95)	3,11,99,132	3,12,82,848		33	32	Information is not available
5	PLANET INVESTMENTS & FINANCE PVT LIMITED (Trading Period-4 th April, 2011 to 7 th June, 2011).(Trading Avg. Price-Rs. 12.5 to 4.83)	1,28,47,418	1,00,93,771	27,53,647	8.92	8.86	9.12
6	VANRAJSINGH KAHOR (Trading Period-26 th July, 2011 to 14 th September, 2011). (Trading Avg. Price-Rs. 4.21 to 3.05)	78,98,609	48,79,736	30,18,873	3.8	3.40	4.44
7	SYNDICATE NIRMAN PVT.LTD (Trading Period-8 th July, 2011 to 6 th September, 2011).(Trading Avg. Price-Rs. 5.66 to 3.10)	45,27,913	42,07,795	3,20,118	4.59	4.18	10.01
8	KAPIL VIJAY AGRAWAL (Trading Period-9 th Nov., 2010 to 24 th Nov., 2010).(Trading Avg. Price-Rs. 36.23 to 23.89)	65,48,810	62,48,810	3,00,000	30.81	30.60	35.12
9	EPOCH SYNTHETIC PVT LTD (Trading Period-7 th Nov., 2010 to 8 th April, 2011).(Trading Avg. Price-Rs. 61.99 to 10.95)	18,28,500	5,94,500	12,34,000	29.30	51.93	18.40
10	KOYAL FINVEST PVT LTD (Trading Period-14 th June, 2011 to 8 th July, 2011).(Trading Avg. Price-Rs. 5.65 to 5.07)	44,47,161	39,02,080	3,00,000	5.38	5.30	5.98

*: More number of shares are sold than bought. May be due to discrepancies in input data. NSE data is from IPO date whereas BSE data is only of last one year.

(ii) GDR Dumping:

In the process total share capital increased by 12 cr and money close to Rs 316 Cr was raised by the company. During first GDR proceed, GDRs seem to have been issued at discounted prices in comparison to Indian market price, whereas the second GDR proceed looks to have been issued on par with the then market price.

TABLE 3: TOTAL GDR ISSUED FOR FOREIGN INVESTMENT IN THE STOCK

Date	GDR Issued	Rate	Remarks
5 th Aug., 2010	40 Lac	USD 7.25 per GDR	This means addition of 4 cr shares to the share capital and money raised through this proceed is USD 29 Millions (which is equal to roughly Rs 125 Cr at 1 USD = Rs 43). The scrip was trading around Rs 35 per share in Indian market at that time.
14 th Dec., 2010	Additional 80 Lac	USD 5.55 per GDR	This means addition of 8 cr shares to the share capital and money raised through this proceed is USD 44.4 Millions (which is equal to roughly Rs 191 Cr at 1 USD = Rs 43). The scrip was trading around Rs 24 per share in Indian market at that time.

Money raised through GDRs at an average price close to Rs 30 per share. Total GDRs raised were 12 Cr share equivalents. Then price started falling down and ultimately saw its bottom at 65 paise on 25th Nov 2011. Price was manipulated downward while GDRs were being dumped in to the market. On 2nd Nov 2011, only 16.76% of GDRs were there with the custodians. Shares available at dirt cheap prices were accumulated and being converted to GDRs now. From 2nd Nov till date, GDRs with custodians has increased from close to 17% to 61%. GDR data as updated on 15th March 2012, it has increased from 52.07% to 61% of total share capital. In terms of total GDRs, it is 78.58%. Current share equivalent of GDRs is 9,429,951 out of 12 Cr total GDRs raised and against total share capital of 15,45,18,600. Without any surprise, the latest GDR holding is 61%, The detail are shown in Table 4 below:

TABLE 4: GDR RISE

S.No.	Date	GDR Value
1	2 nd Nov 2011	16.78%
2	8 th Nov 2011	23.46%
3	31 st Dec 2011	27.97%
4	12 th Jan 2012	45.48%
5	16 th Feb 2012	52.07%
6	15 th March 2012	61 %

According to **Table 3 & 4**, one can predict that GDRs were dumped at higher levels and bought back at dirt cheap prices. Now the question arises: Why does a GDR share holder sell at price less than the buying price and why does he again try to buy at much lower levels?

(iii) Management is not trustworthy to investors:

Management announced the Board Meeting to occur in August 2011, to consider the Bonus issue, twice they postponed the meeting and the reason they are giving is non availability of Directors[16]. If ever they had given some genuine reason, the investors could have understood. The said reason is as if they are fooling the investors.

- When the investors could see fraudulent trading entities resorting to deliberate price manipulation of the scrip by means of bulk deals, why management observed silence?
- Price was hitting almost continuous lower circuits in the past couple of months till it reached all-time low of Rs 0.65 in BSE on 25th Nov 2011. Management knows the names of the trading entities possibly involved in price manipulation, upon analyzing trading data from NSE & BSE for more than an year. What did the management do after knowing the names of those trading entities?
- The investors expected from the management to at least approach the regulator in ensuring that such entities be banned from further trading. Hence, management’s claim that they value investors/shareholders interest is seen as not convincing.

- Management's claim that there is no evidence on insider trading needs to be further confirmed by disclosing holdings of promoters, management, their friends and relatives (both in India and abroad) since capital is raised through GDR proceeds, to make the investors fully convinced.
- Investors strongly feel that, had the management come public on business channels and provided future performance guidance immediately after price fell below its face value, the situation would have not worsened as is the case now.
- Management's claim that telecom industry turmoil as the possible reason is not convincing because other peers performance is not affected equally adversely.
- Though the claim of diversification by management looks good, why it took so long to provide critical information such as this earlier, when the price fell below its face value.
- Investors are also seeking answers to management's decision to consider bonus issue, and then decision on disapproving the same. Investors were shell shocked to know that the board meeting got postponed twice and later got cancelled due to non-availability of its directors. This shows how committed the management is in investor interests.

(iv) **SEBI's Investigation:**

There are lot of complains[15] of investors against Nutek India Limited regarding price manipulation and deep fall in share price. SEBI investigation, is going on. In future we shall work on the issue and try to investigate on conceptual/Financial/ economic point of view and prepare a statistical report to examine whether there is some fraud/ manhandling in the stock is made.

Some research work and reports in this direction, have been mentioned in references [1]-[11] below.

4. Conclusion:

The principle goal of the present research is to offer the detection of price manipulation in a security, in this context we have studied and analyzed the data of Bulk Deals and GDR data of Nutek India Limited and we have seen how the share price fallen from its IPO listing price Rs 192 to Rs 0.65 due to price manipulation by operators, how GDR were dumped at higher levels and bought back at dirt cheap prices. Management made false statements regarding bonus issue and never bothered about deep fall in share price since IPO, hence Management is not trustworthy to investors. SEBI investigation is going on, yet the outcome of investigation has not come.

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